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A Novel Framework for Realistic 3D Skin Modeling and its Exposure to Millimeter Waves

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ABSTRACT Millimeter wave (MMW) technology is increasingly used in telecommunications and medical applications, necessitating a deeper understanding of its interaction with human tissue, particularly skin. The limited penetration depth of MMWs makes the skin the primary site of energy absorption, requiring detailed dosimetric analysis. Traditional skin models often assume planar, layered structures, neglecting the natural undulating geometry of the epidermis and dermis. This study introduces a novel methodological framework for constructing realistic three-dimensional (3D) human skin models using Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) and Ultrasound (US) imaging. The framework involves three key steps: (1) OCT and US image acquisition, (2) image segmentation and processing, and (3) synthesis of processed data to generate high-fidelity 3D skin models. Three anatomical sites—the volar forearm, hypothenar region, and fingertip—were selected for model development, representing variations in skin roughness and layer composition. The dielectric properties of the skin and subcutaneous layers were incorporated into finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) simulations at 27.5 GHz to evaluate the impact of skin roughness on electromagnetic field distribution. Our results demonstrate that the natural undulations of the dermoepidermal junction and air-skin interface significantly affect MMW energy absorption patterns. The roughness of these interfaces varies across anatomical sites, influencing local electric field distributions and leading to deviations from predictions based on planar models. The findings suggest that incorporating realistic skin geometries enhances dosimetric accuracy, which is critical for both safety assessments and optimizing MMW-based medical applications. This study provides an approach for individualized MMW dosimetry and underscores the importance of considering anatomical variations in electromagnetic exposure assessments. The framework was additionally extended to a nodular basal cell carcinoma case, revealing marginal changes in local field and SAR distributions and a moderate increase in reflected power compared to healthy skin.

INDEX TERMS Dosimetry, electromagnetic fields (EMF), 5G, 3D skin modeling, BCC, millimeter waves (MMW).

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing telecommunication needs in terms of high data rates, reduced latency, and numbers of connected

devices, have led to the utilization of the upper part of the non-ionizing electromagnetic spectrum, i.e., that of millimeter waves (MMW). At this frequency range, the penetration depth

of electromagnetic fields inside human tissue is limited to a few millimeters [1]. As a result, skin is the organ that absorbs most of the electromagnetic energy and needs to be studied for potential biological effects at MMW [2].

A significant number of dosimetry studies have emerged in the literature pertaining to both human [1], [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], and animal [14], [15], [16], [17], [18], [19], [20], [21], [22], [23], [24] skin. Many of them apply planar layered skin models (multilayer slabs) [1], [3], [4], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [21], [24] with some including measurements for validation [3], [11], [13], [21]. Others employ artificial human 3D skin models [5], [6], [8], [12] mainly aiming to study the dosimetry of skin appendages (e.g., sweat glands). An important point missed by all the above approaches is that melanocytes, Merkel cells and basal cells, all responsible for different types of skin cancer, are in the basal (deepest) layer of the epidermis, which is not planar but undulant. The undulating nature of superficial skin layers can also become important at body sites like the fingertips. However, the significance of this layer shape for the absorbed electromagnetic energy at MMW has not been studied, yet.

Recent studies have highlighted the importance of individualized approaches in safety and medical applications [25]. To improve dosimetric accuracy at frequencies above 6 GHz, researchers emphasize the need for higher-resolution, body-region-specific skin models [26]. Furthermore, incorporating realistic variations in skin thickness can further enhance both electromagnetic (e.g., power absorption) and thermal (e.g., the insulating effect of the fat layer) dosimetry [27], [28].

The aim of the present work is to provide a methodological framework for the improvement of skin dosimetry under MMW exposure by employing the development of realistic 3D human skin models based on optical coherence tomography (OCT) and ultrasound imaging (US) data. The proposed framework offers two primary contributions to dosimetry. First, it enhances microdosimetry by incorporating the undulating geometry of the superficial skin layers (i.e., SC and VE). Second, it facilitates an individualized, body-region-specific approach to dosimetric evaluation. This reduces the uncertainty resulting from unknown variations in layer thickness across different individuals and body regions, a factor widely recognized as critical in both electromagnetic and thermal modeling. This individualized approach has already been successfully applied in the 'SEAWave-Clin' clinical study [29]. Furthermore, the framework can help overcome the resolution limitations of routine medical imaging used to create anatomical models [30]. Finally, we believe that this framework opens the way for highly accurate, patient-specific dosimetry in medical applications utilizing millimeter waves (MMW), thereby improving treatment efficacy [31].

This framework is then applied to three different body sites to obtain dosimetry results for plane wave exposure at 27.5 GHz. A case including a pathological skin condition (Basal Cell Carcinoma, BCC) is also studied. These case studies are intended to illustrate the applications of the proposed framework and are not exhaustive.

FIGURE 1. Steps for 3D skin model building: (a) OCT and US image acquisition, (b) segmentation of OCT scan images (top) and measurement (bottom) of the distance from air to dermis-fat interface (green) and air to fat-muscle interface (red), and (c) data synthesis and 3D model generation.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. MODEL BUILDING FRAMEWORK

Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) is a medical imaging technique based on the principle of Michelson interferometry, commonly used for non-invasive investigation of tissues in ophthalmology and dermatology [32]. The resolution of an OCT scan image ranges from 1 μm for ultra-high-resolution systems (e.g., LC-OCT [33]) to around 20 μm and is superior to that achieved by other tomographic methods such as conventional ultrasound [34]. On the other hand, it offers a moderate penetration depth of approximately 1.5 mm [32]. OCT enables the visualization of different skin strata (e.g., stratum corneum (SC), epidermis, dermis) and some cutaneous appendages (e.g., hair follicles, eccrine sweat ducts, sebaceous glands) [34]. It also provides useful visual information pertaining to inflammatory skin diseases and tumors [32].

Compared with OCT, ultrasound (US) imaging offers a substantially higher penetration depth at the expense of reduced resolution. For instance, a 15MHz ultrasound device has a penetration depth of approximately 2.5cm and a resolution of 0.1 mm [35]. Consequently, US can provide imaging of deep skin regions (e.g., deep dermis (DE)) and subcutaneous tissues (e.g., fat (FT), muscle (MS), bone (BN)) but with substantially lower detail compared to OCT.

The proposed framework for realistic 3D skin model building consists of 3 major steps: (a) OCT and US image acquisition, (b) image processing (measurement and segmentation), and (c) processed data synthesis (Fig. 1).

The image acquisition process includes OCT and US scanning of the target skin region. In this study, the OCT scan was performed using a multi-beam, swept-source system from Vivosight (Vivosight, Michelson DiagnosticTM Inc., Kent, United Kingdom). The scanning area was 6 mm \times 6 mm and 120 consecutive images of skin vertical cross sections (Fig. 1(b), top) were acquired, offering a resolution of approximately 5 μm \times 50 μm \times 5 μm up to a depth of 1 mm. The US image (Fig. 1(b), bottom) was acquired using an Esaote MyLab X6 system (Esaote S.p.A., Genoa, Italy) with a transducer (AL2442), offering a resolution of 0.1 mm up to a depth of 30 mm.

The segmentation process involves OCT images only. Based on the identification of skin layers presented in [34] for

different body sites, three interfaces are identified and marked on each OCT image (Fig. 1(b), top): (a) air to stratum corneum (SC), (b) stratum corneum to viable epidermis (VE), and (c) viable epidermis to dermis, also known as dermoepidermal junction (DEJ). The data for each of the three interfaces mentioned above, are then combined for the 120 consecutive images (Fig. 1(a)) to form three different surfaces, using code developed in MATLAB (The MathWorks Inc., Natick, MA, USA). It should be noted here that the US imaging, due to its higher penetration depth compared to OCT, is used only for the measurement of the thicknesses of DE and FT layer. However, the significantly lower resolution of US does not allow for accurate 3D model building. Consequently, the DE-FT and FT-MS interfaces are considered planar (Fig. 1). An exception is made for the DE-FT interface in the fingertip model (Fig. 1(b)) which is considered non-planar, due to the high undulating nature of the overlying layers and the relatively small thickness of the dermis.

The three different skin interfaces produced in the segmentation process above are then imported, in an STL (stereolithography) file format, into Sim4Life (ZMT, Switzerland) software. Using the CAD tools available and the US imaging measurements, the final 3D model is constructed (Fig. 1(c)).

&BGR; AUTOMATIC SEGMENTATION OF OCT IMAGES

The segmentation process described in the previous section is often performed manually and therefore requires significant time and effort. In this section, we present a deep learning-based methodology for the automatic segmentation of OCT images.

Initially, a dataset of 2400 grayscale OCT images was collected and manually annotated to establish the ground truth lines for two anatomical interfaces: the air–SC boundary and the DEJ. Manual segmentation was performed directly on each image by tracing two lines corresponding to the aforementioned boundaries. The annotated dataset was randomly divided into 70% training, 15% validation, and 15% testing subsets. The training set was used to optimize the model parameters, the validation set supported hyperparameter tuning and early stopping, and the independent test set was reserved for the final performance assessment. Automatic line detection was performed using a Residual Encoder–Decoder Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) designed for pixel-wise segmentation [36], [37]. The implemented network follows a residual encoder–decoder architecture composed of convolutional residual blocks. Each block includes convolutional layers with normalization and ReLU activation together with shortcut connections that facilitate gradient propagation. Downsampling in the encoder is performed using max-pooling layers. The decoder restores spatial resolution through upsampling layers. The network outputs a pixel-wise probability map through a sigmoid activation function, and model training is performed using the Adam optimizer with binary cross-entropy loss. The encoder extracts hierarchical, multi-scale features, whereas the decoder reconstructs a full-resolution 2D probability map in which

FIGURE 2. Epidermis–dermis junction: (a) Prediction by CNN. (b) After local smoothing based on stability analysis.

each column represents the probability distribution of the line-point positions. Residual blocks [38] and skip connections [39] were incorporated to enhance gradient flow and preserve fine spatial details. The final line is obtained by selecting, for each column, the pixel with the maximum probability value. The deep learning model is used solely to extract anatomical interfaces from OCT images; the subsequent electromagnetic simulations are performed independently using the resulting geometrical contours. The model achieved high segmentation performance, with pixel-wise accuracy exceeding 99% for the air–SC boundary and approximately 98% for the DEJ on the independent test set. Although the predicted lines closely followed the ground truth, a small number of localized discontinuities (“spikes”) were occasionally observed, particularly in low-contrast or structurally complex regions.

To correct the small localized spikes occasionally produced by the CNN predictions, a local smoothing procedure was applied as a post-processing step. The CNN output—a 2D probability map—is first examined through a Local Stability Analysis, which evaluates the reliability of each column’s prediction based on four criteria:

- i) small vertical change relative to neighbouring columns ($\leq 4\text{px}$),
- ii) proximity to a rolling median estimate ($\leq 3\text{px}$ deviation),
- iii) sufficiently high peak probability (≥ 0.2), and
- iv) clear separation from the second-highest probability (≥ 0.05).

Columns satisfying all criteria are classified as stable and are retained without modification. Columns that violate one or more criteria are considered unstable and undergo further optimization. Localized smoothing is then applied exclusively to these unstable regions using a Viterbi-based dynamic programming algorithm [40], which identifies the most probable continuous line path across columns while preserving the original stable segments. This combined procedure effectively suppresses spikes and produces smooth, anatomically coherent lines.

Fig. 2 illustrates a representative example of DEJ segmentation. Panel (a) shows the initial line predicted directly by the CNN, where minor localized discontinuities can be observed at the right end of the image. Panel (b) presents the corresponding result after applying the proposed local smoothing based on stability analysis, demonstrating effective suppression of spikes while preserving the underlying anatomical structure.

TABLE 1. Relative Permittivity, Conductivity and Mass Density Values for Each Skin Layer and Subcutaneous Layers at 27.5 GHz

Skin / Subcutaneous layer	Relative permittivity	Conductivity (S/m)	Mass density (kg/m ³)
SC, stratum corneum	3.58	1.13	1500
VE, viable epidermis	16.66	19.28	1109
DE, dermis	19.63	24.40	1109
FT, fat	3.54	2.19	911
MS, muscle	23.53	37.42	1090
BN, bone (cortical) [46]	5.21	4.89	1908
BCC [41]	22.68	28.24	1109

C. DIELECTRIC PROPERTIES

Except for the geometric model, an electromagnetic simulation requires the definition of the dielectric properties (i.e., permittivity, electrical conductivity) of its constituting materials (skin and subcutaneous layers). Therefore, the permittivity and electrical conductivity of SC, VE, DE, FT, BN and MS layers need to be defined.

SC is the outermost skin layer consisting of keratinized cells with a low water content [1], [10]. The dielectric parameters used in [1], [9], [10], [41] evaluated for the frequency of 27.5 GHz are applied in the current work (Table 1). The remaining part of the epidermis, called viable epidermis (VE), has no blood supply, yet significantly higher water content [1]. Dermis (DE), the outermost perfused skin layer, has a water content close to that of VE [10] which has led to the use of identical dielectric properties for these two distinct layers in [1], [9], [10]. However, *in vivo* confocal Raman spectroscopy measurements of water content in human forearm skin [42], show, except for a dramatic increase from SC to VE, a small increase as depth increases thereafter. This could be reasonably attributed to the DE layer, which is in line with the measurements in [43] that are applied in our model at 27.5 GHz. It should be noted here that water content variations occur in a rather continuous way [42], [44] within skin layers, which are considered distinct in the present study. Therefore, dielectric properties are expected to follow the same smooth variation. To mediate the impact of this observation on dosimetry, further division of each skin layer can be applied as in [6], [45]. Additionally, the water content (hence the dielectric properties at MMW) of skin layers can vary depending on other parameters like age [9], [44], body site [42], use of local drugs or moisturizing creams [3], even the time of the day [44]. Indeed, the impact of the variations of dielectric properties on dosimetry metrics remains outside the

FIGURE 3. 3D skin models for 3 different body sites: (a) hypothenar region, (b) volar forearm, and (c) fingertip. Skin and subcutaneous layers are marked with different colors: SC (pink), VE (cyan), DE (orange), FT (purple), MS (dark red) and BN (white).**TABLE 2. Thicknesses (μm) of Skin and Subcutaneous Layers for the 3 Different 3D Models**

Skin / Subcutaneous layer	Hypothenar region	Volar forearm	Fingertip
SC, stratum corneum	267.9 [47]	21.5 [48]	317.3 [47]
VE, viable epidermis	156.6 [49], [50]	88.4 [49]	264.4 [49], [50]
DE, dermis	775.5 [50]	830.2 [51]	618.1 [50]
FT, fat	5100	2360	1500
MS, muscle	4000	4000	-
BN, bone	-	-	4000

scope of this work. The applied values of relative permittivity, conductivity and mass density are summarized in Table 1.

D. MODEL METRICS

Following the procedure described above, three different skin models of a healthy middle-aged Caucasian male volunteer were created: (a) volar forearm (Fig. 3(a)), (b) fingertip (Fig. 3(b)), and (c) hypothenar region (Fig. 3(c)).

Cases (a) and (c) correspond to “thick skin” and case (b) to “thin skin” [34], as can be observed in terms of SC and VE thicknesses in Fig. 3. Skin ridges (cases (a) and (c)) and sweat pores (case (a)) are also identifiable. This fact enables the realistic positioning of sweat gland ducts (acrosyringium) beneath each sweat pore (not shown here). This skin appendage is of particular interest from a dosimetry point of view, due to its helical structure and dielectric properties [5], [6], [7], [8], [12], [45]. Different roughness of skin interfaces at different body sites is also captured using the proposed method (e.g., Fig. 2(c), higher undulation of superficial skin layers at the fingertip).

The roughness of the air-skin interface and the DEJ was calculated as a measure of the undulating nature of the superficial skin layers and is presented in Table 3. The surface

TABLE 3. Roughness of Skin Interfaces for the Three Different 3D Models

Interface	Roughness measure	Fingertip	Hypothenar region	Volar forearm
Air – skin interface	Ra (μm)	37.6	27.7	11.2
	Rq (μm)	46.7	33.7	14.3
Dermoepidermal junction	Ra (μm)	14.6	14.6	10.8
	Rq (μm)	17.3	17	13.4

FIGURE 4. 3D skin model of nodular Basal Cell Carcinoma (BCC) shown in blue color, generated using the proposed framework.

characterization is based on the vertical deviations of the roughness profile from the mean line. Ra is the arithmetic mean deviation, i.e., the arithmetic average of profile height deviations from the mean line. Rq is the quadratic mean, i.e., the root-mean-square average of profile height deviations from the mean line [52]. It is clear that the site of the volar forearm presents the smallest roughness at the surface of the skin (air-skin interface), but also further inside at the dermoepidermal junction (DEJ).

A skin model of a pathological condition—specifically, nodular Basal Cell Carcinoma (BCC)—was also built using the proposed framework (Fig. 4). The dielectric properties of the “malignant BCC” group in [41] were applied to the volume occupied by BCC, whereas values of Table 1 were applied to the remaining skin layers. A mass density of 1109 kg/m³, (i.e., the mass density of both VE and DE layers) was considered for the BCC.

E. ELECTROMAGNETIC SIMULATION

The electromagnetic (EM) simulation was performed using the Finite Differences in Time Domain (FDTD) method, implemented in the Sim4Life software platform. A linearly polarized plane wave source of 1 V/m in amplitude, propagating along z-axis, with the electric field (E-field) vector parallel to the x-axis, at 27.5 GHz was used (TE-polarization).

FIGURE 5. Fingertip skin model alteration procedure to apply PBCs: (a) Original model, (b) flattened model (produced by detrending), (c) flattened and undistorted model, and (d) symmetric model (produced by mirroring model c).

At this frequency, for the fingertip model (Fig. 3(c)), the lower wavelength inside the tissues is that in dermis (DE), λ_{DE} :

$$\lambda_{DE} = \frac{\lambda_0}{\sqrt{\varepsilon_{DE}}} = 2.46 \text{ mm} \quad (1)$$

where λ_0 the wavelength in free space, λ_{DE} the wavelength in the DE layer, and ε_{DE} the relative permittivity of the DE layer. A common practice is to select the grid size of the computational domain so that the $\lambda/10$ rule-of-thumb is satisfied to reduce numerical dispersion of the FDTD method [53], [54]. However, in order to capture the model’s structural details, a grid size of 0.02 mm was selected as will be explained later in more detail. Perfectly Matched Layers (PMLs) were applied at the top and bottom of the model (parallel to xy plane) and Periodic Boundary Conditions (PBCs) on the sides (parallel to xz and parallel to yz planes). The application of PBCs assumes that a single unit cell of the computational domain can be simulated instead of a large periodic structure [55]. However, in our case the single unit cell is neither perfectly symmetric nor can it reproduce the large-scale geometry of a fingertip when repeated in space. To avoid the aforementioned problem, the following approach is followed: The large-scale curvature of the model is initially removed by detrending, then corrected for distortion and finally mirrored sequentially at planes parallel to xz and yz planes. Thus, a flat (in terms of large-scale curvature), undistorted and symmetric unit cell of the computational domain, appropriate for PBCs application is created. This procedure and its impact on the E-field distribution in the VE layer is shown in Figs. 5 and 6, respectively. It should be mentioned that this model is considered appropriate for assessing the variations in dosimetry resulting from the undulating boundaries of the skin layers only, i.e., the small-scale curvature of skin layers (thus, only fit for assessing micro-dosimetry), under plane wave incidence, and not for assessing the variations in dosimetry due

FIGURE 6. Electric field distribution inside the VE skin layer per area volume (normalized), for various skin models of the fingertip presented in Fig. 3 plus a planar equivalent model.

to the large-scale skin curvature that changes at different body locations [56].

Taking a closer look at the electric field (E-field) distribution per volume area for the VE skin layer (Fig. 6) we can make the following comments: a) The E-field distributions of all models (Fig. 6) depart significantly from the one in the planar equivalent model (i.e., the model with planar interfaces of skin layers and equal volume—for each layer—with the original one) and include both lower and higher E-field values. b) The broadening of the E-field distribution in the original model is significantly reduced in the flattened models. This fact highlights the necessity of flattening the original model in order to simulate a small skin sample by applying PBCs and avoid large errors induced by repeating a non-symmetric cell. c) The removal of the distortion produced in the flattening procedure, further enhances dosimetry. d) The consideration of a symmetric model (Fig. 5(d)) has only a marginal impact on dosimetry. As a result, the flattened-undistorted model can be considered sufficient, also offering the advantage of reducing computational resources by a factor of four compared to the symmetric one.

Additionally, the impact of the grid size on dosimetry metrics (i.e., E-field) was evaluated. A uniform grid was applied, and the grid step was progressively decreased ($\lambda_{DE}/5$, $\lambda_{DE}/10$, $\lambda_{DE}/40$, and $\lambda_{DE}/400$, where λ_{DE} is the wavelength inside the DE layer. The variations of the E-field distribution (normalized per volume area), for plane wave incidence of 1V/m in amplitude, were studied (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7 shows that the distribution of E-field values inside VE layer converges for grid step lower than $\lambda_{DE}/40$ (i.e., 62 μm). This value is lower than $\lambda_{DE}/10$ which is often used for homogenous media [54], [55]. This very small grid step is necessary to efficiently capture the model resolution (5 $\mu\text{m} \times 50 \mu\text{m} \times 5 \mu\text{m}$) and the thicknesses of the skin layers (Table 2). Yet, the resulting, computationally intensive grid can be mitigated using other techniques (e.g., non-uniform grid). The value of 20 μm was selected for the grid step, as a compromise between computational error and required simulation time.

Finally, we investigated the impact of staircasing artifacts inherent in the FDTD method [57]. Typically, finer

FIGURE 7. Electric field distribution normalized per volume for different grid sizes, inside the VE layer for the flattened-undistorted model of the fingertip. Grid size is expressed as a fraction of the minimum wavelength inside the dermis layer (λ).

FIGURE 8. Electric field distribution normalized per volume inside the VE layer, as evaluated using the FDTD (blue line) and FEM (red line) methods.

discretization mitigates these staircasing effects [57]; however, reducing the FDTD grid size beyond $\lambda_{DE}/40$ did not significantly alter the E-field values (as demonstrated by the $\lambda_{DE}/400$ distribution in Fig. 7). To verify this and to accurately model the curved boundaries of the skin layer interfaces, the Finite Element Method (FEM) [58] was employed. A simplified skin model was created in COMSOL Multiphysics by extruding a 2D vertical skin cross-section into the third dimension, to balance computational cost with geometric precision. A comparison of the two computational methods shows only marginal differences in the resulting E-field distributions (Figs. 8 and 9).

F. VALIDATION

Power reflection measurements were conducted to validate the simulation framework. However, because these measurements are macroscopic, they only validate the framework's application at that specific scale. To our best knowledge, non-invasive *in vivo* validation of microscopic geometric effects on dosimetry remains infeasible. In this context, three healthy volunteers (one male and two females) first had the skin on their right upper arms scanned using both OCT and US. Their imaging data

FIGURE 9. Colormap of electric field on a cross-sectional plane of the simplified skin model, as evaluated using the FDTD (right) and FEM (left) methods.

FIGURE 10. Power reflection coefficient as evaluated from VNA measurements (continuous lines) and from simulation data using 3D realistic skin models and a WR28 waveguide model (continuous lines with squared markers).

were then used to construct a 3D skin model for each individual, following the proposed framework. On the scanned area of each volunteer’s inner right arm, a WR28 waveguide was subsequently placed, and power reflection measurements were performed using a portable vector network analyzer (VNA). The measurement frequency range was 21-42 GHz.

Measurement and simulation data for the power reflection coefficient are in good agreement (within $< 14.6\%$, or 0.6 dB) across the frequency range considered (Fig. 10). The observed differences can be attributed to uncertainties induced by the dielectric properties values of the skin layers used in the analysis. It is worth noting that the authors in [11] adopted dielectric property values approximately 20% higher than those reported in the literature to obtain improved agreement with the measurement results.

In Fig. 11 the E-field values of a 1 W/m^2 TE₁₀ propagating mode at 27.5 GHz both inside the WR28 waveguide and a volunteer’s 3D skin model are shown.

III. RESULTS

As can be inferred from Fig. 6, the distribution of the E-field values in the fingertip 3D model departs from the one pertaining to the widely used planar model. This fact can also

FIGURE 11. Colormap of electric field (logarithmic scale) on a cross-sectional plane of the waveguide-3D skin simulated model at 27.5 GHz used for comparison with the measurement data.

FIGURE 12. Colormaps of electric field (top) and voxel SAR (bottom) values in a plane parallel to the xz-plane for the fingertip models: realistic (left) and planar (right). Values correspond to an incident plane wave of 1V/m in amplitude and 27.5 GHz in frequency, propagating along z axis. The electric field is linearly polarized parallel to x axis.

be observed in Fig. 12 and Table 4 regarding both E-field and specific absorption rate (SAR) values.

In Fig. 13, the E-field values (magnitude) for three different body sites (i.e., volar forearm, hypothenar region and fingertip) are plotted, using colormaps, for a planar cross section

TABLE 4. Statistical Comparison of Electric Field and Voxel SAR Values Between Two Different Models of the Fingertip

E-field Statistics (V/m)	Planar Equivalent model				3D Realistic model			
	min	max	mean	std dev	min	max	mean	std dev
Skin Layer								
Stratum Corneum	0.392	0.588	0.486	0.060	0.193	1.200	0.514	0.070
Viable Epidermis	0.250	0.382	0.314	0.041	0.107	0.769	0.308	0.045
Dermis	0.202	0.243	0.221	0.014	0.193	0.337	0.222	0.015
Fat	0.147	0.240	0.201	0.029	0.147	0.241	0.200	0.029
Bone	0.034	0.146	0.076	0.032	0.034	0.147	0.075	0.032
voxel SAR statistics (mW/kg)								
Skin Layer								
Stratum Corneum	0.058	0.130	0.091	0.022	0.014	0.543	0.101	0.027
Viable Epidermis	0.544	1.271	0.872	0.227	0.100	5.146	0.843	0.273
Dermis	0.437	0.634	0.526	0.067	0.412	1.250	0.546	0.074
Fat	0.026	0.070	0.049	0.014	0.026	0.070	0.049	0.014
Bone	0.001	0.027	0.009	0.007	0.001	0.028	0.009	0.007

FIGURE 13. Colormaps of electric field inside realistic 3D skin models at a plane parallel to the xz -plane for different body sites: (a) Volar forearm (left), (b) hypothenar region (middle), and (c) fingertip (right). Values correspond to an incident plane wave of 1V/m in amplitude and 27.5 GHz in frequency, propagating along z axis. The electric field is linearly polarized parallel to x axis.

of the 3D model, parallel to the plane where the E-field and direction of propagation lie. Large differences in skin layers thicknesses and boundaries are present between different body sites. A remarkable difference in SC thickness is also obvious between thick skin (fingertip, hypothenar region) and thin skin (volar forearm) body sites. The impact of the aforementioned differences and skin layers interfaces' geometry on dosimetry can be observed in the colourmaps of Fig. 13.

For the BCC case study, only marginal differences in both the electric field and the induced SAR values are observed

FIGURE 14. Colormaps of electric field values inside realistic 3D skin models at a plane parallel to the xz -plane for nodular BCC (left), and with no tumor included (right). Values correspond to an incident plane wave of 1 V/m in amplitude and 27.5 GHz in frequency, propagating along z axis. The electric field is linearly polarized parallel to x axis.

(Figs. 14-15). At 27.5 GHz, a moderate increase in the reflected electric field and a corresponding decrease in SAR values are observed in the tissue layers superficial to the BCC region.

IV. DISCUSSION

A framework for realistic 3D skin model creation using OCT and US imaging data was presented. The framework enables

FIGURE 15. Colormaps of SAR values inside realistic 3D skin models at a plane parallel to the xz -plane for nodular BCC (left), and with no tumor included (right). Values correspond to an incident plane wave of 1 V/m in amplitude and 27.5 GHz in frequency, propagating along z axis. The electric field is linearly polarized parallel to x axis.

a detailed dosimetry assessment of the human skin under MMW exposure by considering both skin layers' thicknesses and skin layer interfaces' microgeometry. These factors tend to have a significant variation among different body sites and different individuals with a corresponding impact on dosimetry at MMW exposure and higher frequencies. The main findings indicate the presence of extreme local values of dosimetric quantities in the superficial skin layers (e.g., VE) compared to planar layered skin models, while mean values remain unchanged. The framework also enables individualized dosimetric assessment of the exposed skin region, thereby improving accuracy by reducing uncertainty in the knowledge of skin layer thicknesses, a known key determinant of dosimetric quantities.

However, the proposed framework cannot be used for a dosimetry assessment that considers the large-scale curvature of skin (e.g., [56], [59]), as described in Section II-D. This is an expected result, since the total skin region scanned with OCT (6 mm \times 6 mm), is inadequate to capture the large-scale curvature variations to an adequate extent.

E-field and SAR values in Table 4 and Fig. 12 show differences in dosimetry when considering a 3D skin model, compared to the planar one. These differences are larger for the SC and VE layers, lower in DE and marginal for subcutaneous layers (FT, MS and BN). The differences refer to the minimum, maximum and standard deviation of the distribution, whereas mean values are largely maintained. For example, in the case of the finger and inside the VE layer, the ratio E_{\max}/E_{\min} takes a value of 7.2 in the realistic 3D model, compared to 1.5 in the planar equivalent model. This difference shows that the microgeometry of the skin layers interfaces', which is present in the 3D model, describes the actual exposure conditions in the skin, which can be highly non-uniform. It should be noted that the differences evaluated above correspond to a specific individual and a single body region; therefore, they do not capture population-level variability in dosimetric quantities, but serve primarily to demonstrate the usability of the proposed framework.

Physically, the most pronounced local E-field maxima and minima are localized at the SC-VE interface (Figs. 12-13) due to two key factors: this boundary exhibits both the highest

dielectric contrast (Table 1) and the most severe structural undulations (similar to air-SC interface, Table 3). The extreme values are fundamentally driven by electromagnetic boundary conditions, specifically, the required continuity of the normal electric displacement field across the interface. Because the undulating geometry continuously alters the local surface normal, it dictates how the incident E-field is partitioned into normal and tangential components along the boundary. At points where the geometry maximizes the normal component, the large dielectric contrast forces a sharp discontinuity in the E-field, generating highly localized extreme values. However, because these localized maxima and minima are strictly dependent on the alternating spatial orientations of the interface curvature, they offset each other when spatially averaged. Consequently, the mean E-field values remain largely unchanged relative to uniform planar models.

The biological significance of this finding remains to be investigated, but the maximum values of the electric field appear in the areas where critical cell types are located, i.e., at the basal layer of the VE (basal cells, melanocytes, Merkel cells) or slightly above it in the stratum spinosum (squamous cells). Moreover, in the VE region several free nerve endings and keratinocytes lie, which play an important role to nociception and neuroinflammation [60].

A case involving the most frequent skin cancer type (i.e., BCC) was also modelled by applying the proposed framework. The dosimetry evaluations revealed marginal differences regarding E-field and SAR distribution, whereas a moderate increase in reflected power, also reported in [41], was found.

V. CONCLUSION

The scope of this work was to propose a framework for dosimetric calculations of electromagnetic fields at the MMW range by building realistic 3D skin models.

The proposed framework can capture the geometrical characteristics of the upper skin layers (i.e., SC, VE and DE) in high detail, so that skin roughness and its underlying geometry are modelled efficiently. The impact on dosimetry of the undulations at the layers' interfaces was evaluated, yielding both lower and higher values for the E-field and SAR, compared to the equivalent planar models. This improvement of absorbed energy evaluation could provide useful insight in regions of biological interest. An example could be the VE region where free nerve endings and keratinocytes lie, which play an important role to nociception and neuroinflammation [60].

The proposed 3D skin modelling method can also be extended to include the dosimetry study of pathological skin conditions, like BCC. Another potential field of application is THz skin sensing [61].

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